

Synthesis of Compounds related to Reserpine Skeleton : I

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Condensation of N-phthaloylphenylalanine with methyl anthranilate led to methyl N-phthaloyl-phenylalanyl-anthranilate, which on hydrazinolysis afforded methyl phenylalanyl-anthranilate. Reduction with lithium aluminium hydride furnished α -(*o*-hydroxymethyl-anilino) methyl- β -phenylethyl amine, which on Pictet-Spengler cyclisation afforded 3-(*o*-hydroxymethyl-anilino)methyl 1,2,3,4-tetrahydroisoquinoline. Treatment of diethyl acetamidobenzylmalonate with formalin and HCl led to 1,2,3,4-tetrahydroisoquinoline-3-carboxylic acid. Direct dehydrogenation to isoquinoline-3-carboxylic acid was effected with sulphur in dimethylformamide. Condensation *via* its mixed carbonic-carboxylic acid anhydride derivative gave methyl N-(3-carboxyisoquinolino) anthranilate.

In search of effective reserpine substitutes, syntheses of compounds related to its component fragments have been carried out extensively¹. The model compounds were prepared by dissecting out the portion of the pentacyclic system responsible for biological activity. The hypothetical cleavage of the molecule depending on the lines of cleavage gives rise to several pattern of compounds, many of which have been synthesised and evaluated. However, molecular modification of the reserpine structure, have not yielded any compound of material advantage, so far.

Synthetic studies in the model of the presumed biogenetic pathway of many natural products, or utilising the presumed biogenetic precursors, have culminated in many elegant syntheses and have attracted wide-spread attention in recent years. Excellent reviews^{2, 3, 4} on biogenetic theory and biogenetic-type synthesis have appeared recently.

Tryptophan is assumed to be the precursor of a large group of indole alkaloids. The fact that anthranilic acid is intimately bound up with tryptophan metabolism, and consequently related biogenetically to the much larger and wide-spread group of alkaloids, has been well established⁵. It was accordingly thought of interest to synthesise compounds in which the indole part of the reserpine skeleton replaced by anthranilic acid moiety or structures closely related to it and the rings D and E by the biologically important phenylalanine.

1. (a) T. Kralt, *et al.*, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1961, **80**, 313; 1966, **85**, 607; (b) S. de Groot and J. Strating, *ibid.*, 1961, **80**, 121; (c) J. Gootjes and W. Th. Nautga, *ibid.*, 1966, **85**, 966; and leading references cited therein.
2. R. Robinson, *The Structural Relations of Natural Products*, Clarendon Press, Oxford, 1955.
3. E. E. van Tamelen, *Fortschr. Chem. Org. Naturst.*, 1961, **192**, 42.
4. E. Leete in A. Weissberger ed., *Biogenetic Theory in Structural Elucidation* (Vol. XI, Part-1, of *Technique in Organic Chemistry*), Interscience, New York, 1963, Ch. VII.
5. J. R. Price, *Fortschr. Chem. Org. Naturst.*, 1956, **13**, 302.

N-Phthaloylphenylalanine⁶ (I) was condensed with methyl anthranilate to furnish methyl N-phthaloylphenylalanyl anthranilate (II) using the mixed carbonic-carboxylic acid anhydride. However, the reaction using N-phthaloylphenylalanyl chloride gave higher yields. Hydrazinolysis of II, at room temperature, afforded methyl phenylalanyl anthranilate (III), isolated as the free base as well as hydrochloride. Formylation of III furnished the formyl derivative (IV) which was not accessible utilising the 'mixed anhydride' method using formylphenylalanine⁷. On warming with formalin, methyl phenylalanyl anthranilate hydrochloride afforded methyl N-(1,2,3,4-tetrahydroisoquinoline-3-carboxy) anthranilate (V).

In another sequence of reactions methyl phenylalanyl anthranilate was treated with lithium aluminium hydride in tetrahydrofuran or ether at room temperature, to afford α -(hydroxymethylamino)methyl- β -phenylethylamine (VI), thus effecting concomitant reduction of the carbomethoxy group and the amide linkage. Methyl formylphenylalanyl anthranilate (IV) on lithium aluminium hydride reduction gave the corresponding N-methyl derivative (VII). Conductometric studies indicated that the above-mentioned diamines formed monohydrochlorides. Pictet-Spengler cyclisation of V furnished the corresponding tetrahydroisoquinoline derivative (VIII).

6. A. K. Sen and S. Sarma, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **44**, 644; 1968, **45**, 17.

7. cf.: F. E. King, J. W. Clark-Lewis, D. A. A. Kidd and G. R. Smith, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 1039.

Isoquinoline-3-carboxylic acid (X) has previously been made in several steps^{8,9}. Fruitful dehydrogenation of the easily accessible 1,2,3,4-tetrahydroisoquinoline-3-carboxylic acid would likely be a more convenient synthesis. Dehydrogenation of compounds containing a carboxylic acid group, as such, suffers from a disadvantage in their susceptibility to undergo concomitant decarboxylation. Our attempts to dehydrogenate 1,2,3,4-tetrahydroisoquinoline-3-carboxylic acid (IX) using sulphur in tetralin at 150° resulted in the recovery of the starting material. Use of dimethylformamide as solvent effected the dehydrogenation to furnish isoquinoline-3-carboxylic acid in 40% yield. During the course of the above investigation it was observed that prior hydrolysis and decarboxylation for the formation of phenylalanine from its precursor diethyl acetamidobenzylmalonate for the synthesis of 1,2,3,4-tetrahydroisoquinoline-3-carboxylic acid does not appear to be a prerequisite for smooth Pictet-Spengler reaction to the corresponding isoquinoline derivative. On treatment with formaldehyde and HCl, diethyl acetamidobenzylmalonate afforded directly the desired 1,2,3,4-tetrahydroisoquinoline-3-carboxylic acid (IX) as hydrochloride in good yield. Acylation of methyl anthranilate with isoquinoline-3-carboxylic acid to afford methyl N-3-carboxyisoquinoline anthranilate (XI) was achieved through the 'mixed anhydride' procedure. In spite of the competing reaction for urethan formation the amide was obtained in fair yield. This is possibly due to the increased electron deficiency of the heteroaroyl carbonyl carbon atom compared to aroyl carbonyl carbon atom¹⁰.

Attempts to condense methyl phenylalanyl anthranilate with methyl α -bromo- β -methoxypropionate have resulted in the recovery of the starting material, when organic solvents were used as condensing medium. The components, however, when heated in a sealed tube furnished an extremely hygroscopic compound, presumed to be methyl N-[(α -carbomethoxy- β -methoxy) ethyl] phenylalanyl anthranilate hydrobromide. Conversion to the hydrochloride did not offer any advantage.

8. C. E. Teague and A. Roe, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, **73**, 688.

9. F. H. Case, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1952, **17**, 471.

10. cf.; D. S. Tarbell and N. A. Leister, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1958, **23**, 1152.

EXPERIMENTAL*

Methyl N-phthaloylphenylalanyl anthranilate (II) : (a) A solution of N-phthaloylphenylalanine⁶ (4.9 g., 0.016 mole) in dry chloroform containing triethylamine (1.6 g., 0.016 mole) was cooled to 0°. Ethyl chloroformate (1.8 g., 0.016 mole) was added to the stirred reaction mixture during 15 min. After a further period of 15 min., methyl anthranilate (2.4 g., 0.016 mole) was added dropwise and the temperature was then allowed to attain the room temperature (25°) during 2 hr. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the residue triturated with water. The sticky mass, which turned crystalline on scratching with methanol, was collected and recrystallised from methanol, (yield 70%) m.p. 161°. Infrared bands were found at 1770, 1709, 1681, 1605, 1595, 1534, 1449, 1429 cm⁻¹. (Found : C, 70.40; H, 5.05, Calc. for C₂₃H₂₀N₂O₅ : C, 70.09; H, 4.67%).

(b) A solution of N-phthaloylphenylalanyl chloride¹¹ (15.65 g., 0.049 mole) in dry chloroform (75 ml) was added dropwise with stirring to a solution of methyl anthranilate (15.1 g., 0.10 mole) in chloroform (50 ml) during 2 hr. the temperature being maintained at 20–25°. The mixture was evaporated to dryness under reduced pressure, residual mass triturated with two portions of dilute hydrochloric acid (10 ml; 1%) followed by water till free from acid and recrystallised as described above, yield 18.7 g. (87%). Mixed melting point determination of the two samples recorded no depression.

Methyl phenylalanyl anthranilate (III) : Hydrazine hydrate¹² (99%) (1.35 g., 3 eqv.) was added to a solution of methyl N-phthaloylphenylalanyl anthranilate (10.7 g., 0.022 mole) in dry chloroform (50 ml) and kept at room temperature (25°) with stirring for 2 days. Phthalhydrazide, which separated was filtered off and weighed 3.7 g. (91%). The filtrate was taken to dryness at room temperature *in vacuo*, and the gummy residue was taken up in methanol (25 ml.). The white crystalline methyl phenylalanyl anthranilate (III), obtained on chilling the solution for 2 days, was recrystallised from methanol (4.0 g., 54%), m.p. 73°. Infrared bands were found at 3200, 1695, 1681, 1603, 1582, 1527, 1502, 1445, 1429 cm⁻¹. (Found : C, 68.71; H, 6.27; N, 8.90. Calc. for C₁₇H₁₈N₂O₃ : C, 68.45; H, 6.04; N, 9.39%).

The mother liquor from the above preparation was acidified with conc. hydrochloric acid (congo red) and evaporated to dryness. The solid was dissolved in methanol, diluted with excess ether when an additional amount of methyl phenylalanyl anthranilate separated out as its hydrochloride and recrystallised from methanol, yield, 2.3 g. (28%), (overall yield 82%), m.p. 192°. (Found : C, 61.41; H, 5.78. Calc. for C₁₇H₁₈N₂O₃Cl : C, 60.98; H, 5.68%).

Methyl N-formylphenylalanyl anthranilate (IV) : Methyl phenylalanyl anthranilate (III) (1.5 g., 0.005 mole) was heated on a water bath with formic acid (98%, 2 ml) for 2 hr. and triturated with crushed ice. The white solid was collected and washed with water (1 g., 63%). Recrystallisation from methanol gave an analytical sample, m.p. 134°. Infrared bands were found at 1704, 1689, 1645, 1603, 1536, 1511, 1449 cm⁻¹. (Found : C, 66.49; H, 6.03; N, 8.27. Calc. for C₁₈H₁₈N₂O₄ : C, 66.26; H, 5.52; N, 8.59%).

*All melting points are uncorrected. Infrared spectra were determined (KBr discs) on Perkin-Elmer Infracord. Model 137.

11. J. C. Sheehan and V. S. Frank, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, **71**, 1856.

12. L. I. Smith and K. L. Howard, *Organic Syntheses*, 1944, **24**, 53.

Methyl N-(1,2,3,4-tetrahydroisoquinolino-3-carboxy)anthranilate hydrochloride (V): A mixture of methyl phenylalanyl anthranilate (III) hydrochloride (1 g., 0.003 mole) and formaldehyde solution (40%; 2 ml) was heated on a steam bath. After an hour an additional amount of formaldehyde (1 ml) was added and the heating continued for 2 hr longer. The solution was taken to dryness under reduced pressure, treated with water and again taken to dryness. The compound on crystallisation from methanol yielded white crystalline solid, m.p. 190°; yield, 400 mg. (40%). Infrared bands found at 1733, 1715, 1603, 1495 cm^{-1} . (Found: C, 62.99; H, 6.02; N, 8.60. Calc. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{Cl}$: C, 62.33; H, 5.48; N, 8.08%).

*α -(*o*-Hydroxymethyl anilino)methyl- β -phenylethylamine hydrochloride (VI)*: A solution of methyl phenylalanyl anthranilate (III) (2.98 g., 0.01 mole) in dry tetrahydrofuran (15 ml) was added dropwise with efficient stirring to a slurry of lithium aluminium hydride (4.5 g., 0.12 mole) in tetrahydrofuran (50 ml) during 30 min. at room temperature (25°). After the addition has been completed the stirring was continued for a further period of 5 hr. The reaction mixture was then decomposed by careful addition of water (11 ml) and stirred for 30 min. The white curdy mixture was filtered, washed with two 5 ml portions of tetrahydrofuran. The filtrate and washings were dried (Na_2SO_4) and solvent removed. The residual oil was dissolved in methanol and acidified with conc. hydrochloric acid to afford the monohydrochloride as yellowish white solid, 2.2 g. (75%), m.p. 280–281° (dec). Crystallisation from methanol did not raise the melting point. Infrared bands were found at 3333, 3247, 2985, 2874, 1605, 1587, 1515, 1497, 1475, 1466 cm^{-1} . The percentage of chlorine determined by conductometric titration with silver nitrate solution was 12.21; Calc. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_2\text{O Cl}$: Cl, 12.13%. (Found: C, 65.40; H, 7.63; N, 8.87. Calc. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{21}\text{N}_2\text{O Cl}$: C, 65.64; H, 7.17, N, 9.57%).

*α -(*o*-Hydroxymethyl anilino)methyl- β -phenyl-*N*-methylethylamine hydrochloride (VII)*: The procedure as adopted in the case (VI) for reduction with lithium aluminium hydride was employed using methyl *N*-formyl phenylalanyl anthranilate (IV) (1 g., 0.003 mole) and lithium aluminium hydride (1.7 g., 0.044 mole) in tetrahydrofuran. The residue was dissolved in methanol, acidified with methanolic-HCl, excess ether was added and chilled. Decantation of the solvent left a gummy residue which turned crystalline on drying in a vacuum desiccator. The hydrochloride was highly hygroscopic. The percentage of chlorine determined as precipitated silver chloride was 12.02; Calc. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{23}\text{N}_2\text{OCl}$: Cl, 11.58%.

*3-(*o*-Hydroxymethyl anilino)methyl 1,2,3,4-tetrahydroisoquinoline (VIII)*: A mixture of α -(*o*-hydroxymethyl anilino) methyl- β -phenylethylamine hydrochloride (VI) (1.45 g., 0.005 mole), aqueous formaldehyde (38%, 3 ml) and conc. hydrochloric acid (0.5 ml) was heated on a steam bath. After one hour a further amount of formaldehyde (1.5 ml) was added and heating continued for 2 hr. longer. The clear solution was evaporated to dryness under reduced pressure. The residue was triturated with water, taken to dryness and the process was repeated for a second time. The hydrochloride was dissolved in methanol, filtered to remove insoluble material, if any, diluted with ether and cooled. The thick oil obtained after decanting off the solvents, afforded crystalline solid (1.5 g., 98%) on keeping under vacuum in a desiccator. The hydrochloride was crystallised from water, m.p. > 350°.

An aqueous solution of the hydrochloride was basified with a slight excess of aqueous ammonia. The free base which separated as a voluminous yellowish precipitate was collected. The compound, which appeared to retain water tenaciously, was dissolved in benzene and diluted with ether and chilled. The shining yellow crystalline solid was collected. An analytical sample was dried for several hr. at 135–140° under vacuum, m.p. 178° (dec.), (Found : C, 76.31; H, 7.84; N, 10.49 Calc. for $C_{17}H_{20}N_2O$: C, 76.12; H, 7.46; N, 10.44%).

1,2,3,4-Tetrahydroisoquinoline-3-carboxylic acid (IX) : A mixture of diethyl acetamidobenzymlonate¹³ (15.4 g., 0.05 mole), aqueous formaldehyde (38%) (30 ml) and conc. hydrochloric acid (75 ml) was warmed on a steam bath with stirring. After 3 hr. a further amount of formaldehyde (15 ml) and conc. hydrochloric acid (30 ml) was added and heating continued for another 3 hr. During the initial stages brisk evolution of gas occurred and separation of white crystalline solid set in. The mixture was chilled overnight, filtered, dried and crystallised from dilute hydrochloric acid (2%); yield 8.0 g. (92%), m.p. 307–309° (dec). The reported melting point is 308–309° (dec).¹⁴

1,2,3,4-Tetrahydroisoquinoline-3-carboxylic acid was obtained by neutralising the hydrochloride essentially as described by Julian *et al.*¹⁵, m.p. 322–324° (lit. 326°).

Isoquinoline-3-carboxylic acid (X) : A mixture of 1,2,3,4-tetrahydroisoquinoline-3-carboxylic acid (IX) (7.08 g., 0.04 mole) and sulphur (5.2 g.) in dimethylformamide (40 ml) was heated in an oil bath at 145–150° with stirring for 3 hr. during which there was copious evolution of H_2S . Solvent was removed under reduced pressure and the residue extracted with five 10 ml portions of warm water and filtered. The resulting turbid solution was boiled with charcoal, filtered hot and taken to dryness on a steam bath. The sticky residue turned crystalline on scratching with a little water, filtered and dried, yield, 1.75 g., m.p. 160–162°. The mother liquor was acidified with dil. hydrochloric acid and taken to dryness on a steam bath. The residue was dissolved in 25 ml of water, filtered and neutralised to congo red with aqueous ammonia (10%). After cooling, a second crop of the crystalline product was collected, 1.0 g. (overall yield, 40%). Crystallisation from water raised the melting point to 165–166°; the reported⁹ melting point is 167–168°. Infrared bands were found at 3450, 2985, 1655, 1635, 1588, 1538, 1494 cm^{-1} .

Methyl N-(3-carboxyisoquinolino)anthranilate (XI) : A solution of isoquinoline-3-carboxylic acid (X) (1 g., 0.005 mole) [dried at 110° under vacuum for several hr.], and triethylamine (0.58 g., 0.005 mole) in dry chloroform (15 ml) was cooled to 0°. Ethyl chloroformate (0.62 g., 0.005 mole) was added dropwise during 10 min. with efficient stirring. After stirring at that temperature for 30 min., a solution of methyl anthranilate (0.88 g., 0.005 mole) in chloroform (10 ml) was added, care being taken so that the temperature does not rise above 5° and stirring was continued for 3 hr. longer. Solvent was evaporated off under reduced pressure and the residue was washed with three 5 ml portions of cold water, warmed with methanol (15 ml), cooled and filtered. Recrystallisation of the residue from a large volume of methanol (100 ml) afforded colourless needles, m.p. 167°, yield 500 mg.; 30%. Infrared bands were found at 1702, 1684, 1590, 1516, 1460 cm^{-1} . (Found : C, 70.77; H, 5.11; N, 8.92. Calc. for $C_{18}H_{14}N_2O_3$: C, 70.58; H, 4.57; N, 9.15%).

13. A. J. Zambito and E. E. Howe, *Organic Syntheses*, 1960, **40**, 21.

14. A. Archer, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1951, **16**, 430.

15. P. L. Julian, W. J. Karpel, A. Magnani and E. W. Meyer, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 180.

Attempted Condensation of methyl phenylalanylthranilate with methyl α -bromo- β -methoxypropionate : A mixture of methyl phenylalanylthranilate (III) (1.5 g.; 0.005 mole) and methyl α -bromo- β -methoxy propionate¹⁶ (1.0 g.; 0.005 mole) was heated in a sealed tube at 120–125° for 14 hr. The resinous material was washed off with three 5 ml portions of ether, dissolved in methanol, charcoaled and filtered. The solvent was removed and the mass was treated with water (10 ml), basified with a slight excess of ammonia and extracted with chloroform. Dark gummy mass (insoluble in ether), left on removal of chloroform, was redissolved in methanol, acidified with methanolic-HCl to congo red, diluted with excess ether and chilled. The glassy material obtained, on drying the separated gum, was found to be exceedingly hygroscopic.

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16. H. E. Carter and H. D. West, *Organic Syntheses*, Coll. Vol. 3, 1955, 774.